

Thermal structure of the Qaanaaq Ice Cap outlet glaciers, north-western Greenland

Version 1

Description

The aim of the project is to investigate the thermal structure, ice thickness, surface topography, and drainage system of the three largest outlet glaciers of the Qaanaaq Ice Cap. Although peripheral glaciers are especially sensitive to climate change, contributing to sea level rise and serving as an important freshwater resource, they are typically studied only at the the Greenland Ice Sheet scale. The thermal regime of peripheral glaciers remains poorly understood, hindering reliable future projections. Within the scope of this project, two expeditions will be carried out in 2026 and 2027, during which ground-penetrating radar, unmanned aerial vehicles, and passive seismic methods will be used.

The project will provide new knowledge about the current state of the glaciers, advancing understanding of Arctic glacier dynamics, their response to climate change, and their impact on the local Qaanaaq community. All collected data will be openly accessible and used both in scientific research and public outreach, supporting Arctic research and the dissemination of knowledge in Latvia, Greenland, and beyond.

Funder

Latvian Council of Science | | LCS LZP

Grant

Researchers

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Organizations

University of Latvia

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [Thermal structure of the Qaanaaq Ice Cap outlet glaciers, north-western Greenland](#)

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Organizations:

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: [Latvian Council of Science](#) | [LCS](#)

Grants: [LZP](#)

Project:

3. License

License: [CC-BY-4.0](#)

Access Rights: [Public](#)

Publication Date: [2026-03-17](#)

4. Templates

Descriptions

[GPR Dataset for Qaanaaq Ice Cap Outlet Glaciers, NW Greenland](#)

Raw georeferenced ground-penetrating radar (GPR) profiles collected during two field campaigns (August 2026 and August 2027) on the three largest outlet glaciers of the Qaanaaq Ice Cap (Fan Glacier, Sydgletscher, and an unnamed glacier), northwestern Greenland.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 [What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?](#)

The data are collected to characterise the ice thickness, internal thermal structure, basal conditions, and subglacial topography of the three largest outlet glaciers of the Qaanaaq Ice Cap. These measurements directly address the project's core objective of assessing the polythermal regime of High Arctic glaciers and testing existing model assumptions about the relationship between ice thickness and thermal structure. The data originate from in-situ GPR surveys conducted on glacier surfaces during two summer field campaigns.

1.1.2 [Type of data generated/collected](#)

- Observation data

- Other

In-situ geophysical observations

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- CSV
- Others

SEG-Y

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

50

GB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

No suitable existing GPR datasets covering the three target glaciers are available.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The dataset will be directly useful to glaciologists studying High Arctic glacier dynamics, thermal regimes, and mass balance. It will also be of value to researchers working on ice thickness and glacier bed topography modelling, climate impact assessments in the Arctic, and water resource management for communities depending on glacial meltwater. The Qaanaaq local community and Danish authorities responsible for infrastructure and flood risk management may also benefit from improved understanding of glacier drainage behaviour derived from this data.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

Dublin Core

Dataset metadata will follow Dublin Core standards as supported by the Zenodo repository. A README file will accompany the deposit describing coordinate reference systems, trace header byte locations for GNSS coordinates in SEG-Y files, antenna frequency, acquisition parameters, and processing steps applied.

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

An embargo is applied until submission of the associated peer-reviewed articles, expected no later than December 2028. This protects the scientific priority of the

research team while ensuring data are openly available in a timely manner consistent with LCS open science requirements.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org>

Zenodo is a free, open-access repository supported by OpenAIRE. It supports DOI assignment, versioning, Dublin Core metadata, and long-term preservation. It is widely used in glaciology community.

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

SEG-Y files can be opened with any SEG-Y compatible software. CSV files can be opened in any spreadsheet or data analysis software.

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.2.7 Other relevant remarks

GPR data processing is performed using Prism 2.7 (Radar Systems Inc.), which is commercial software. However, all processing parameters and steps will be fully documented in the README file, enabling reproduction of results with equivalent software.

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

SEG-Y is an open industry-standard format supported across geophysical software platforms. CSV outputs are open formats compatible with GIS software and standard data analysis tools. The dataset can be combined with surface elevation data (ArcticDEM), ice velocity datasets, and other geophysical datasets for integrated glacier modelling.

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.3.3 Other relevant remarks

No formal controlled vocabulary standard exists for GPR glaciological data. Terminology follows conventions established in the glaciological literature, particularly the methodological frameworks described in associated peer-reviewed publications.

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

CC BY 4.0 is selected to maximise reuse potential while ensuring appropriate attribution to the research team. This is consistent with LCS open science policy and Zenodo best practices.

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

The dataset is intended for long-term reuse by the glaciological research community. Zenodo provides persistent storage and DOI resolution beyond the project lifetime.

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2028-12-01

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

Zenodo provides indefinite storage. The dataset is expected to retain scientific value for at least 10 years given the scarcity of in-situ glacier measurements in this region.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

No

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

Costs related to data management, processing, and preparation for deposit are covered by the project personnel budget funded by the Latvian Council of Science grant. Open-access publication fees are covered by a dedicated publication cost budget line within the project. Zenodo deposit is free of charge.

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Lelde Švinka (0009-0005-3158-0508)

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Zenodo provides free long-term storage with no ongoing costs required. No additional financial resources are needed to maintain dataset accessibility after project completion.

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Physical access control

The dataset contains no personal, sensitive, or confidential information and therefore requires no specialised security measures. Raw data are backed up daily on multiple external drives during fieldwork to prevent loss. Upon return, data are transferred to the University of Latvia Polar Research Centre servers protected by standard institutional password access. The dataset is intended for full open access upon deposit in Zenodo and no access restrictions are planned beyond the embargo period.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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